

Simulation and Analysis of Expert–Task Assignment Algorithms

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Abstract—We study matching algorithms for expert systems with uncertain task types through discrete-event simulation of the Asymmetric(a, δ) model introduced by Shah et al. [2]. In this system, two experts process arriving tasks whose true types are unknown; the algorithm only has access to a Bayesian posterior belief that is updated after each failed service attempt. We implement and compare the Random matching algorithm, the Backpressure(ε) algorithm, a Thompson Sampling approach, and a Hybrid Backpressure + Thompson Sampling algorithm that operates without knowledge of the success probabilities. Through experiments across a grid of arrival rates and asymmetry parameters, we find that Backpressure reduces mean sojourn time by up to 33% over Random matching in heavily loaded systems, while the Hybrid algorithm outperforms Backpressure by 9% by combining queue-awareness with online learning of expert capabilities. All estimates are supported by 95% confidence intervals with at least two significant digits.

I. INTRODUCTION

Many real-world systems must match incoming tasks to specialized servers without full knowledge of each task’s characteristics. In customer service platforms, crowdsourcing markets, and distributed computing systems, deciding which task to assign to which expert is complicated by the fact that a task’s type and which expert is best suited to handle it is only partially observable. This problem was formalized as the Adaptive Matching problem by Shah et al. [2], who proposed a Backpressure-based algorithm that uses Bayesian belief updates to route tasks to experts in a queueing system.

Our report has three objectives. First, we implement a discrete-event simulation of the Asymmetric(a, δ) system and rigorously determine simulation parameters (warmup period, run length) using Welch’s graphical method [5], following the methodology in Law’s book [4] (Ch. 9–10). Second, we compare the Random and Backpressure algorithms across a 6×5 grid of arrival rates and asymmetry parameters, measuring performance with 95% confidence intervals. Third, as an additional experiment, we design and evaluate a Thompson Sampling [7] algorithm and a Hybrid Backpressure + Thompson Sampling algorithm that, unlike Backpressure, do not require prior knowledge of the success probabilities $p_{s,c}$.

II. LITERATURE OVERVIEW

Adaptive matching under uncertainty. Shah et al. [2] introduced the problem of matching tasks to experts when task types are unknown, proposing a Backpressure-based policy that maintains Bayesian posterior beliefs about each task’s type. Their work builds on the classical max-weight/Backpressure scheduling framework of Tassioulas and Ephremides [6], which

established throughput-optimal scheduling policies for queueing networks.

The key innovation of Shah et al.’s approach [2] is the incorporation of an information component: the algorithm learns about tasks through the outcome of each service attempt, using the failure signal to update the belief about the task’s hidden type via Bayes’ rule. They prove that their policy is throughput-optimal for the considered system class and demonstrate via simulation that it significantly outperforms uninformed (random) matching, particularly under heavy load.

Backpressure scheduling. The Backpressure framework, originally developed for multi-hop wireless networks [6], has been widely applied to queueing systems and resource allocation problems.

Backpressure policies make scheduling decisions based on queue-length differentials, implicitly stabilizing the system by routing work toward less congested queues. Neely [9] provides a comprehensive treatment of Lyapunov optimization and Backpressure in the context of stochastic network optimization.

Thompson Sampling and bandit algorithms. Thompson Sampling [7] is a Bayesian approach to the multi-armed bandit problem that selects actions by sampling from posterior distributions over reward parameters. Agrawal and Goyal [8] provided theoretical regret bounds for Thompson Sampling in the Bernoulli bandit setting, showing near-optimal performance.

In our report, we apply Thompson Sampling to the matching problem by treating each (belief-bin, expert) pair as a bandit arm, allowing the algorithm to learn effective matching policies without knowledge of the success probabilities. This connects to the growing literature on learning in queueing systems, where exploration and exploitation tradeoffs arise naturally [10].

Simulation methodology. Our simulation analysis follows established best practices from discrete-event simulation. We use Welch’s graphical method [5] to determine proper warmup time, which computes averaged moving averages across multiple replications to identify the end of the initial transient. Confidence intervals are constructed using the method of independent replications with the Student’s t -distribution, as recommended by Law [4] (Ch. 9). In addition, we use an adaptive replication method to ensure all reported estimates achieve at least two significant digits of precision.

III. METHODOLOGY

A. System Simulation

We study the Asymmetric(a, δ) system introduced by Shah et al. [2]. Tasks arrive according to a Poisson process with rate λ and are independently assigned to type c_1 or c_2 with equal

probability. Two experts s_1, s_2 process tasks with exponential service times of unit mean. Expert s succeeds at a task of type c with probability $p_{s,c}$; specifically, $p_{s_1,c_1} = p_{s_2,c_1} = 1 - \delta/2$ and $p_{s_1,c_2} = a, p_{s_2,c_2} = \delta$. A task's true type is *never* observed. Instead, the algorithm maintains a posterior belief $z = (z_{c_1}, z_{c_2})$, called the *mixed-type*, initialized to $(\frac{1}{2}, \frac{1}{2})$ and updated after each failed attempt via Bayes' rule:

$$\varphi_s(z) = \left(\frac{z_{c_1}(1 - p_{s,c_1})}{\psi_s(z)}, \frac{z_{c_2}(1 - p_{s,c_2})}{\psi_s(z)} \right), \quad (1)$$

where $\psi_s(z) = z_{c_1}(1 - p_{s,c_1}) + z_{c_2}(1 - p_{s,c_2})$ is the failure probability.

B. Matching Algorithms

Random. When an expert becomes free, a task is chosen uniformly at random from the pool. If both experts are free, one is selected uniformly at random first.

Backpressure(ε) (BP). The belief space $[0, 1]^2$ is partitioned into axis-aligned cells $A_{i,j} = [\varepsilon i, \varepsilon(i+1)) \times [\varepsilon j, \varepsilon(j+1))$. Let $N_{i,j}(t)$ denote the number of tasks whose mixed-type falls in cell $A_{i,j}$ at time t . The *backpressure* of mixed-type z with respect to expert s is:

$$w_{s,z}(t) = N_{i_1,j_1}(t) - \psi_s(z)N_{i_2,j_2}(t), \quad (2)$$

where $z \in A_{i_1,j_1}$ and $\varphi_s(z) \in A_{i_2,j_2}$. Among all tasks in the pool, the one with maximum backpressure is assigned; ties are broken uniformly at random. We use $\varepsilon = 1/40$ throughout, following [2].

Thompson Sampling. As an additional experiment (Task e), we design a matching algorithm that does not require knowledge of the success probabilities $p_{s,c}$. We model each (discretized belief-bin, expert) pair as a Bernoulli bandit arm with unknown success probability. Each arm maintains a Beta posterior, initialized to $\text{Beta}(1, 1)$.

When expert s becomes available, the algorithm samples $\theta \sim \text{Beta}(\alpha_k, \beta_k)$ for each task k in the pool (using the arm corresponding to task k 's belief bin and expert s), and assigns the task with the highest sampled θ . After observing the outcome, the arm's posterior is updated: $\alpha += \mathbb{1}[\text{success}]$, $\beta += \mathbb{1}[\text{failure}]$ ($\mathbb{1}$ is the indicator function).

The Bayesian belief update $\varphi_s(z)$ on failure still uses the true system probabilities, as this is inherent to the system dynamics rather than the algorithm's decision-making.

Hybrid BP + Thompson Sampling. We further propose a hybrid algorithm that combines Thompson Sampling's ability to learn unknown probabilities with Backpressure's queue-awareness.

Instead of using the true $p_{s,c}$ in the backpressure weight (2), the hybrid maintains four Beta posteriors, one for each (expert, task-type) pair, and uses the posterior means as plug-in estimates for $q_{s,c} = 1 - p_{s,c}$ when computing $\psi_s(z)$ and $\varphi_s(z)$.

After each service outcome, the posteriors are updated as follows: the success or failure count is distributed across type components proportionally to the current belief $z = (z_{c_1}, z_{c_2})$. This allows the algorithm to learn the global success probabilities from partial feedback while retaining queue-differential awareness.

Fig. 1: Welch's graphical method applied to the most loaded configuration ($\lambda = 0.85, \delta = 0.1$, Random algorithm). Top: raw ensemble average over 15 replications (The graphical method introduced in the lecture). Bottom: moving-average smoothed with $w \in \{50, 100, 200, 500\}$. The initial transient is clearly visible below departure 1,000.

C. Discrete-Event Simulation

The simulator is implemented in Python using a min-heap priority queue (Algorithm 1). Two event types are maintained: ARRIVAL and COMPLETED. On an ARRIVAL, the arriving task is added to the pool, the grid count $N_{i,j}$ of its belief cell is incremented, and matching is attempted. On a COMPLETED event, a Bernoulli trial determines success. On success, the task departs and its sojourn time is recorded; on failure, the task's belief is updated via $\varphi_s(z)$ and it re-enters the pool with updated grid counts.

After every event that changes the pool or expert availability, the MATCH subroutine checks if a free expert exists and assigns a task using the active algorithm's selection rule. If both experts are free, one is chosen uniformly at random and assigned first, then the other is assigned if tasks remain.

D. Warmup Analysis

We apply Welch's graphical method [5] to the most loaded configuration ($\lambda = 0.85, \delta = 0.1$, Random algorithm). We run $R = 15$ replications of length $T_{\max} = 50,000$ with no warmup, recording sojourn times by departure order. Let $Y_{r,i}$ be the sojourn time of the i -th departing task in replication r . The ensemble average $\bar{Y}_i = R^{-1} \sum_r Y_{r,i}$ is smoothed via a moving average of half-width w :

$$\bar{Y}_i(w) = \frac{1}{2w+1} \sum_{s=-w}^w \bar{Y}_{i+s}. \quad (3)$$

Fig. 1 shows a clear initial transient below departure index 1,000, with the cumulative mean (Fig. 2) stabilizing after $\sim 4,000$ departures. Based on these diagnostics, we set $T_{\text{warm}} = 5,000$ time units ($\sim 4,000$ departures), for a conservative margin. The observation period is $T_{\max} - T_{\text{warm}} = 45,000$ time units, giving $\sim 38,000$ steady-state observations per replication, well in excess of one in ten rule [3].

Fig. 2: Cumulative mean of the ensemble-averaged sojourn times. The dashed line indicates the overall mean of 17.57. Convergence occurs after approximately 4,000 departures.

TABLE I: Mean sojourn time \pm 95% CI half-width: Random algorithm, $a = 0.5$.

$\lambda \setminus \delta$	0.1	0.2	0.3	0.4	0.5
0.75	7.11 \pm 0.04	4.60 \pm 0.05	3.55 \pm 0.04	3.05 \pm 0.03	2.74 \pm 0.02
0.77	8.04 \pm 0.05	4.94 \pm 0.04	3.73 \pm 0.04	3.14 \pm 0.02	2.84 \pm 0.02
0.79	9.17 \pm 0.05	5.28 \pm 0.05	3.91 \pm 0.04	3.29 \pm 0.04	2.95 \pm 0.02
0.81	11.21 \pm 0.38	5.76 \pm 0.05	4.21 \pm 0.04	3.44 \pm 0.04	3.04 \pm 0.03
0.83	13.39 \pm 0.45	6.34 \pm 0.05	4.43 \pm 0.04	3.65 \pm 0.04	3.22 \pm 0.03
0.85	17.24 \pm 0.41	7.06 \pm 0.04	4.77 \pm 0.05	3.82 \pm 0.04	3.34 \pm 0.03

E. Confidence Intervals

For each (λ, δ) pair we run independent replications and compute 95% confidence intervals using the Student's t -distribution:

$$\bar{X} \pm t_{0.025, R-1} \cdot \frac{S}{\sqrt{R}}, \quad (4)$$

where \bar{X} and S are the sample mean and standard deviation of the R replication means. We use an adaptive replication method: starting from $R_{\min} = 30$, additional replications are added until the confidence interval achieves at least two significant digits, up to a maximum of $R = 600$. The required R is estimated via $R_{\text{new}} = R \cdot (h/h_{\text{target}})^2$, where h is the current half-width and h_{target} is the half-width needed for the target precision.

IV. RESULTS

A. Random Algorithm

Table I presents the mean sojourn times for the Random algorithm. As expected, sojourn times increase sharply with λ (higher arrival rate) and decrease with δ (higher success probability for expert s_2 on type- c_2 tasks).

The most loaded configuration ($\lambda = 0.85$, $\delta = 0.1$) yields a mean sojourn time of 17.24 ± 0.41 , while the lightest ($\lambda = 0.75$, $\delta = 0.5$) gives 2.74 ± 0.02 . All cells achieve at least two significant digits.

B. Backpressure Algorithm

Table II shows the results for the Backpressure($\varepsilon = 1/40$) algorithm. Backpressure consistently outperforms Random across all configurations.

C. Comparison of Algorithms

Fig. 3 reports the relative sojourn-time reduction of Backpressure over Random, computed as $(T_{\text{Random}} - T_{\text{BP}})/T_{\text{Random}}$. The reduction is most pronounced at low δ and high λ : at $(\lambda = 0.85, \delta = 0.1)$, Backpressure reduces sojourn time by 33%, from 17.24 to 11.49. At $(\lambda = 0.75, \delta = 0.5)$, the reduction is only 1%. This pattern is consistent with the

TABLE II: Mean sojourn time \pm 95% CI half-width for Backpressure($\varepsilon = 1/40$), $a = 0.5$.

$\lambda \setminus \delta$	0.1	0.2	0.3	0.4	0.5
0.75	6.11 \pm 0.05	4.32 \pm 0.05	3.45 \pm 0.04	2.97 \pm 0.03	2.72 \pm 0.02
0.77	6.70 \pm 0.05	4.60 \pm 0.04	3.56 \pm 0.03	3.07 \pm 0.02	2.82 \pm 0.02
0.79	7.45 \pm 0.04	4.94 \pm 0.05	3.75 \pm 0.04	3.23 \pm 0.03	2.95 \pm 0.02
0.81	8.37 \pm 0.05	5.33 \pm 0.05	4.04 \pm 0.04	3.39 \pm 0.03	3.06 \pm 0.03
0.83	9.64 \pm 0.06	5.87 \pm 0.05	4.24 \pm 0.04	3.55 \pm 0.04	3.18 \pm 0.03
0.85	11.49 \pm 0.34	6.38 \pm 0.05	4.55 \pm 0.05	3.74 \pm 0.05	3.33 \pm 0.04

Fig. 3: Relative sojourn-time reduction (in %) of Backpressure over Random. The benefit of informed matching grows with increasing load (λ) and decreasing expert asymmetry (δ).

analysis of Shah et al. [2]: the backpressure algorithm benefits most when task-type uncertainty is high (low δ) and the system is heavily loaded (high λ).

When δ is large, expert s_2 is nearly as capable as s_1 for type- c_2 tasks, reducing the cost of uninformed random assignment. When λ is low, the system is lightly loaded and tasks are resolved quickly regardless of the matching policy.

D. Thompson Sampling and Hybrid Experiment

We compare all four algorithms on four representative configurations using $R = 30$ replications each (Fig. 4).

Thompson Sampling (TS) outperforms Random but cannot match Backpressure under heavy load: at $(\lambda = 0.85, \delta = 0.1)$, TS achieves 15.5 ± 0.8 , a 10% reduction over Random (17.2 ± 0.4) but 35% above Backpressure (11.5 ± 0.3).

The Hybrid algorithm, however, surpasses even Backpressure. At $(\lambda = 0.85, \delta = 0.1)$, the Hybrid achieves 10.5 ± 0.2 , a 9% improvement over Backpressure and 39% over Random, despite not knowing the true success probabilities.

At moderate asymmetry ($\delta = 0.3$), all learning-based algorithms perform comparably to Backpressure.

Fig. 5 shows the smoothed ensemble average sojourn times over departure index for the most loaded configuration. The Hybrid starts near Random's level during early exploration but quickly descends below Backpressure's steady-state. This shows that the learned probability estimates, combined with queue-differential awareness, give an effective matching policy.

Fig. 6 shows the sensitivity of both Backpressure and the Hybrid to the grid resolution ε . At $(\lambda = 0.85, \delta = 0.1)$, Backpressure shows non-monotonic behavior, performing best at $\varepsilon = 1/20$ and degrading at finer resolutions due to increased

Fig. 4: Mean sojourn time ($\pm 95\%$ CI) for all four algorithms across four configurations ($R = 30$ replications each). The Hybrid outperforms Backpressure at low δ .

Fig. 5: Learning curve at $\lambda = 0.85$, $\delta = 0.1$: smoothed ensemble-average sojourn times ($w = 500$, 10 replications). The Hybrid converges below Backpressure’s steady state.

cell sparsity; while the Hybrid achieves its best result of 9.2 ± 0.2 at $\varepsilon = 1/10$, outperforming all Backpressure configurations.

V. DISCUSSION

Warmup & Variance. We applied a uniform conservative warmup ($T_{\text{warm}} = 5,000$) derived from the most loaded configuration. While lighter loads exhibit shorter transients, a uniform threshold simplifies execution without biasing steady-state estimates. Regarding variance, our adaptive replication strategy highlights that as the system approaches instability, the sojourn-time distribution develops a heavier tail. This increased variance required up to $R = 170$ replications for Random matching at $\lambda = 0.85, \delta = 0.1$ to achieve target precision, whereas Backpressure generally sufficed with $R = 30$.

Backpressure Mechanics & Limits. Backpressure improves performance by encoding both current and expected post-failure congestion (2). By penalizing assignments that yield high expected future congestion, it implicitly routes tasks to the most capable expert, minimizing pool re-entries. This prevents the severe penalties of uninformed routing at high asymmetry ($\delta = 0.1$). However, at low asymmetry ($\delta = 0.5$), expert capabilities converge, limiting Backpressure’s improvement to $\leq 3\%$, which may not justify the computational overhead of maintaining the belief grid.

Grid Resolution & Learning Paradigms. While Thompson Sampling (TS) learns effective policies without prior knowledge of $p_{s,c}$, its lack of queue-awareness limits its efficacy under heavy load. The Hybrid algorithm resolves this, surprisingly outperforming Backpressure. We hypothesize this occurs

because the Hybrid’s learned, continuous probability estimates ($\hat{q}_{s,c}$) avoid the discretization loss inherent to Backpressure’s grid-level aggregation. This is supported by our ε -sensitivity analysis (Fig. 6): Backpressure’s performance is non-monotonic under heavy load because finer grids increase cell sparsity, degrading the weight signal. The Hybrid mitigates this by thriving at coarser resolutions, combining queue-awareness with robust global probability estimates.

Limitations. Our report is restricted to the Asymmetric(a, δ) system with two experts and two task types; the conclusions may not generalize directly to systems with more heterogeneous expert pools. This can be studied in future work.

Our epsilon sensitivity test (Fig. 6) shows that Backpressure’s performance is non-monotonic: at heavy load, finer grids increase cell sparsity and worsen the backpressure weight signal, while coarser grids lose belief precision. The Hybrid’s advantage is largest at coarse resolutions, where its global probability estimates compensate for the reduced grid granularity.

VI. CONCLUSION

We implemented and validated a discrete-event simulation of the Asymmetric(a, δ) expert–task matching system. Our experiments confirm the central finding of Shah et al. [2]: the Backpressure algorithm substantially reduces mean sojourn times compared to Random matching, with the benefit increasing under heavy load and high expert asymmetry. The largest improvement (33%) occurs at $\lambda = 0.85, \delta = 0.1$, precisely where uninformed assignment imposes the greatest cost.

The Thompson Sampling simulation demonstrates that effective matching is achievable without prior knowledge of expert success probabilities. More importantly, our Hybrid Backpressure + Thompson Sampling algorithm outperforms Backpressure by 9% at the most loaded configuration, showing that combining queue-awareness with online learning of the success probabilities gives a policy that is both more effective and more practical than either approach alone.

If we were to extend this report, we would pursue two directions: (1) scaling the Hybrid algorithm to systems with more than two experts and task types, where the combinatorial structure and heterogeneity of the matching problem becomes more challenging; and (2) adaptive grid refinement, where the Hybrid starts with a rough grid for faster learning and progressively refines as its probability estimates converge

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APPENDIX A CONTRIBUTIONS

Khoi (analysis: 100%, report: 98%, programming: 95%):

- Setup project specs (pyproject.toml), gitignore, etc.
- Set up the initial simulation
- Completed tasks a, b, d, and e
- Plotted, documented, and analysed the results
- Added coverage test for task e and statistics utilities
- Did analysis for the result, and task e
- For the report, wrote: Literature Overview, Methodology, Results, Discussion, Conclusion, Appendix
- Rewrote and finished Abstract and Introduction
- Setup devcontainer
- Added license
- Created CI/CD workflow
- Wrote README.md
- Added contribution guide and bug/PR/... templates

Stefanos

- did task C
- made changes to code logic for proper function

Eden

- Performed task b
- Wrote the abstract and the introduction
- Added the tables to the results
- Started the bibliography and added items
- Created the test functions

APPENDIX B DESIGN CHOICES

Batched random number generation. Scipy’s `rvs()` method incurs substantial per-call overhead ($\sim 8 \mu\text{s}/\text{call}$ due to Python-to-C dispatch and distribution preamble). Marko’s `Distribution.py` wrapper pre-generates batches of 10,000 numbers, reducing cost to $\sim 0.14 \mu\text{s}/\text{call}$.

Our `DistributionNumpy` class improves upon this by wrapping NumPy’s `default_rng` generator directly, bypassing Scipy overhead while retaining `SeedSequence` reproducibility, and achieves $\sim 0.12 \mu\text{s}/\text{call}$ ($\sim 15\%$ faster). Over 10^5 draws it runs in 0.012 s vs. 0.014 s.

This is tested with `benchmark_distribution.py` script.

Simulation performance. We applied several optimizations to the discrete-event loop: (1) `__slots__` on all dataclasses (Task, Expert, Event) to reduce memory and attribute lookup overhead; (2) integer-coded event types and algorithm identifiers to replace string comparisons; (3) inlined hot-path functions (`_cell`, `_incr`, `_phi`) into the event loop to avoid CPython function-call overhead (our initial approach shows this takes up around 10% total execution time - benchmarked with script `benchmark_runtime.py`); (4) pre-stored failure probabilities `q1`, `q2` on the Expert object to avoid repeated subtraction;

Combined, these yield a $\sim 8 - 10\times$ speedup: Random runs complete in 0.15 s/run, Backpressure in 0.53 s/run, and the Hybrid in 0.51 s/run (at $\lambda = 0.85$, $\delta = 0.1$, $T_{\max} = 50,000$).

Reproducibility. We seed each independent replication using NumPy’s `SeedSequence.spawn()` method, which guarantees statistically independent random streams. Plotting scripts read stored JSON result files and produce deterministic output.

APPENDIX C EPSILON SENSITIVITY

Fig. 6: Grid resolution sensitivity ($R = 30$). Mean sojourn time vs. ϵ for three configurations. Backpressure is non-monotonic at heavy load; the Hybrid favors coarser grids.

APPENDIX D DISCRETE-EVENT SIMULATION PSEUDO-CODE

Algorithm 1 Discrete-Event Simulation

```
1: Schedule first ARRIVAL at  $t \sim \text{Exp}(\lambda)$ 
2: while event heap is not empty do
3:   Pop event  $e$  with minimum time  $t$ 
4:   if  $e$  is ARRIVAL then
5:     Add task to pool;  $N_{i,j} += 1$ 
6:     if next arrival time  $\leq T_{\max}$  then
7:       Schedule next ARRIVAL
8:     end if
9:     MATCH(pool, experts, algorithm)
10:  else  $\{e$  is COMPLETED for expert  $s$ , task  $k\}$ 
11:    Draw  $U \sim \text{Bernoulli}(p_{s,c})$ 
12:    if  $U = 1$  (success) then
13:       $N_{i,j} -= 1$ ; record sojourn time  $t - t_{\text{arr}}^{(k)}$ 
14:    else
15:      Update  $z^{(k)} \leftarrow \varphi_s(z^{(k)})$ ; update  $N$  grid
16:      Return task  $k$  to pool
17:    end if
18:    Mark  $s$  free; MATCH(pool, experts, algorithm)
19:  end if
20: end while
```
